

INTERPRETATION OF THE MAIN ORGANIZATIONAL FORM OF IMPLEMENTING “EDUCATION 4.0”

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ABSTRACT

The article draws attention to the reasons that necessitate the existence of “Education 4.0” and its specific features. It is stated that education exists as a superstructure phenomenon of the system (base) of social relations formed in accordance with the challenges of industrial revolutions, is aimed at the development of technological literacy and information culture in learners, the way of its implementation, adequate to the nature of the education system in question, is determined by referring to theoretical and technological foundations, and the organizational form of such a training system (being a component included in the way of implementing education in that system) is a learner-centered subsystem.

In the research work, among the components of the learning process as a way of implementing education, its organizational form is distinguished (in the context of its dialectical relationship with the system in which it is contained and other components within this system) and a scientific interpretation is given to it.

Keywords: industrial revolution; technological literacy; information culture; competence; intellectual skills; modern lesson; thinking; thinking lessons.

Relevance of the research topic. It is undeniable that civilization is developing in stages, adequate to the industrial revolutions. This process is understood as the sharing of human experience (transmission from generation to generation), based on scientific foundations and exists in mutual dialectical dependence with the civilization process. The mentioned eternal dialectic makes it necessary to constantly update the views (approaches, calls) on the theoretical and technological foundations of education and the way of its implementation, and brings the study of problems directly and indirectly related to education, cognitive issues that condition the solution of problems, among the requirements of scientific activity. The improvement of the learning process, which is one of the ways of implementing education, as a perfect system necessitates the formation of its components in an organic relationship with what we have said (adequate to the new challenges of civilization), and the regulation of dialectical dependencies.

It is undeniable that the quality of the organization and management of the educational process, along with many other arguments, depends on the level of understanding of its subject (learner) and his/her awareness of its important features. Therefore, we argue for the relevance of the scientific interpretation of the main organizational form of the implementation of “Education 4.0”.

The purpose of the study is to provide a scientific interpretation of the main organizational form of implementing “Education 4.0”.

Methodological basis of the study. In the process of conducting the research, based on L. Bertalanfi's “Idea of System Analysis” [3; 8] (the idea, which is explained as an attempt to study the properties of an object based on the properties of its parts - italics are ours - F.I., GQ), the “System-structural approach”, which

has been formed as an important branch of dialectics and has risen to the level of its alternative, empirical, empirical-theoretical and theoretical methods of scientific cognition, the internal relationships of the forms of scientific cognition, and various pedagogical and psychological research generalizations were used as a methodological basis.

Interpretation of generalizations on research materials: At different stages of world history, humanity has faced serious changes and achieved results with the reforms carried out. The struggle for the concept of modern education in Azerbaijan began in the late 60s-early 70s of the XX century. The goals of this struggle are conditioned by the system of socio-economic relations that plays a basic role.

Currently, there is such a system as a “techno-democratic-information society” that makes people stronger. Unlike an industrial society, an information society is a more intellectual society and creates conditions for the highly educated, skilled, determined, and comprehensive development of people. Members of a “techno-democratic-information society” must have information culture and technological literacy, otherwise they will not be able to assert themselves as active and creative members of the society in question. Information culture is the knowledge, intellectual skills and habits necessary for a person to adapt to the information society. Technological literacy is the ability of people to use various digital technologies, analyze information, and operate safely in a digital environment. “This skill is not limited to using a computer and the Internet, but also includes: 1) Compliance with digital security and cybersecurity rules; 2) Working with artificial intelligence and automation; 3) Digital analytics and data processing skills; 4) Using cloud technologies; 5) Quick adaptation to new technologies” [5]. Technological literacy includes the ability to use information

and communication technologies. Digital education allows people to participate independently in social life. In addition, the reality of digital education and the digital revolution requires fundamental changes in the forms and methods of moral education, leading to the emergence of digital skills as the most important ability [11;58-64].

It is undeniable that the challenges of each industrial revolution have their own specificities and that these challenges require the necessary competencies. The competencies identified by the Council of Europe for the 21st century person are: 1) literacy competence; 2) multilingual competence; 3) mathematical, scientific and engineering; 4) cultural awareness and self-expression; 5) personal, social and learning-to-learn competence; 6) citizenship competence; 7) entrepreneurial competence; 8) digital literacy competence [4;23]. These are manifested against the background of global changes taking place in the world, and at the same time, they condition the existence of new shades in both information culture and the content of technological literacy.

Against the backdrop of industrial revolutions, educational program developers had to seek answers to the following fundamental questions: 1) What knowledge, skills, and values should be reflected in educational programs?; 2) Will these knowledge, skills, values, and competencies form the necessary life skills in learners?; 3) How can the process of implementing education be made relevant and interesting for learners?; 4) How can assessment (an integral part of the educational process) be made more productive and effective.

In the Education 4.0 approach, it has been determined that an environment - a learning process - will be applied, which focuses on the formation and development of intellectual skills, especially based on the following directions: 1) 3R (Recalling, Relating, Refining) regulating understanding; 2) 3I (Inquiring, Interacting, Interpreting) encouraging research; 3) 3P (Participating, Processing, Presenting) based on drawing conclusions [22; 92-98], [13; 40-45].

Education 4.0, which provides an effective environment for the formation of skills that are manifested as the main quality of an active and creative personality, has the following characteristics: 1) Learning regardless of time and place (lifelong learning, e-learning, etc.); 2) The opportunity to receive personalized education according to the skills and abilities of learners; 3) Taking into account the suggestions of learners when preparing the curriculum; 4) Predominance of project-based learning; 5) Formation of learners' ability to conduct analysis on large-scale data (Big Data); 6) Assessment of learners' knowledge in the process of applying them to projects; 7) Becoming a part of the educational system of emerging new technologies, etc. [11-12].

Experience shows that an effective thinker is able to: formulate and express his/her ideas; plan to make his/her ideas understandable to everyone; organize his/her speech correctly (draw the right conclusions using facts, examples, and justifications; analyze events

correctly; determine where and how to obtain information; use information purposefully; determine the relevance of the transmitted information to the object; form a personal opinion, transfer it to someone else; make judgments; justify his/her ideas; take a divergent or convergent approach to problem solving, etc. [4; 27]

The level of fulfillment of the tasks set for the educational process (the way of implementing education) depends on its components (the content of the educational material, the methods applied and their systematicity, resources, the form of organization) and the existence of dialectical unity between them. Among these components, the form of organization has a certain capacity to condition the said unity. It is no coincidence that many prominent psychologists, educators, methodologists, and teachers with advanced experience have been engaged in the improvement of the form of organization (in particular, the lesson), and this process is still being continued today [14]. The emergence of the term "modern lesson" also arose in the course of research on the improvement of the form of organization of education. If the thesaurus of pedagogical terms most frequently used in the Azerbaijani pedagogical press over the last decade had been accurately defined, it is likely that the meaning of "modern lesson" and the struggle to find the perfect version of the modern lesson would have taken first place among pedagogical research (For more information, see: [7-8]).

According to Professor A. Alizadeh, the word "modern" in the sense of "Modern lesson" has a unique heuristic meaning. "Modern lesson" does not mean "today's lesson". A lesson based on the achievements of the time is called a modern lesson. In this sense, two aspects that are organically connected with each other are usually distinguished. Often, when they say a modern lesson, they understand it only as raising the scientific-theoretical level of the lesson, modernizing it. The lesson should reflect the achievements of the time according to its scientific-theoretical level. This is undeniable. However, explaining the meaning of a modern lesson only in this root would be one-sided. We are talking about a pedagogical phenomenon. The word "modern" also characterizes the lesson. This is true both from a psychological and pedagogical, and linguistic point of view. The lesson becomes modern not only due to its scientific-theoretical level, but also due to its pedagogical concept - its construction with the dimensions of new pedagogical thinking. Modern knowledge with modern methods - modern teaching can be generally characterized as follows [2;18].

By the way, let us emphasize that we prefer to take an oppositional position to the use of the term "modern lesson" (although prominent educators, for example, M.I. Makhmutov, have also prepared a monograph in this direction that has become a standard textbook for many. See: [14]).

According to Azad Mirzajanzadeh, "...if the education of creative, creative-minded individuals and their preparation for life is the main goal in the implementation of general education, then the "modern lesson" should be structurally consistent with the acquisition of that experience by the students... In the "modern

lesson”, “it is necessary to clarify the process of accumulating this knowledge rather than teaching the students knowledge.” Numerous observations and studies show that the knowledge that the student (the student - italics are ours) independently learns during the school years gives very effective results, because this is knowledge that is acquired not at the instigation of anyone (i.e. not at the request of the teacher), but with the desire of his own heart” [3;255].

Schools and higher education institutions should help in the accumulation of all the knowledge necessary for life, the development of the mind, the improvement of creative and effective thinking methods, so that all this becomes a habit, a habit that will constantly accompany a person on his life path, and an impetus for the acquisition of personal behavioral criteria and the formation of an active, deep circle of interest. The point is not in the abundance of knowledge. If this knowledge has not passed through the filter of the personal mind, has not been evaluated and processed there, then a person cannot be a creative personality, regardless of the size of that knowledge. Here it is appropriate to recall the meaningful reasoning of Azad Mirzajanzadeh, which is given below. The academician first asks: “What should be learned?” and answers his question with originality as follows: “Here, a Latin expression comes to mind: Many things, but a little (*Multum, non multa-multum non multa*), that is, not quantity, but quality. It is necessary to acquire such a compact knowledge that it is possible to apply it when making decisions in various circumstances” [3 ; 208].

Our In our information-rich age, the main wealth is not information, regardless of its form, but the living work of the mind (by the way, we note that we appreciate the position of philosophers who put forward the idea that “mind is a combination of the ability to think and resourcefulness”), the thinking brain. Information dies, but the mind and thought live and develop. That is why it is necessary to put into action everything that contributes to this development. A seemingly difficult and “archaic” issue can be a hundred times more valuable than any ready-made information. Thinking, thinking is not observation, but creativity.

Humans use various operations in the process of intellectual activity. The nomenclature of intellectual operations is diverse: analysis, composition, comparison, abstraction, generalization, concretization, classification - the invisible internal regularities of thinking are expressed, first of all, by these operations and processes. The responsibility of intellectual activity of students - the application of acquired knowledge, skills and habits in new conditions, the identification of cause-and-effect relationships, the identification of hidden connections and dependencies, the conclusion, the integration and synthesis of information, the solution of a complex problem, the perception of the main idea, the distinction of differences, sensitivity to contradictions, the search for information in alternative ways, the analysis of the situation, the assessment of both the process and its result, the prediction of the outcome of this or that event, the putting forward of hypotheses, the introduction of the idea into practice, etc. all of this directly

depends on the level of development of intellectual operations. According to M. Lipman, the school should teach children to exercise “good judgment”. When he considered school experience from this perspective, he identified fundamental shortcomings in the traditional didactic system. M. Lipman shows that traditional school education trains thinking and reasoning skills in a limited range of areas, such as reading, writing, speaking, mathematical operations, experiments, etc., but “does very little to develop higher-level skills - logical, critical, creative, conceptual, argumentative, dialogical reasoning”. As a result, thinking develops one-sidedly [2 ; 54-55].

By the way, let us emphasize that at each stage of the development of society, a unique pedagogical thinking is formed, and this pedagogical thinking reflects not only the pedagogical values of society regarding the education of children, but also, perhaps, first of all, its philosophical and psychological values. As society develops, new aspects appear in its educational policy, the stereotypes previously established in pedagogical theory gradually become obsolete, and when it is realized that they are obsolete, a new pedagogical thinking begins to form. It is no coincidence that in our schools, extensive searches are being conducted for the main organizational form of the path to implementing “Education 4.0”, which is formed adequately to the challenges of the “techno-democratic-information” society. From the analysis of the creative searches of advanced teachers in the field of development and education of thinking in students, it is concluded that they have not only mastered the concept of modern education, but also are striving to enrich it further with their unique experience in effective options.

According to our subjective opinion, education is formed as a superstructure phenomenon of the system (basis) of social relations formed in accordance with the challenges of industrial revolutions, the way of adequate implementation of the said educational system is determined by referring to theoretical and technological foundations, the organizational form of such a training system (being the included component) is a learner-centered subsystem (in relation to the educational system). This subsystem is expressed by the vague term - “modern lesson”. Despite what has been said, we consider it acceptable to call the vague term formed as “modern lesson” “thinking lessons” and believe that this term has a more “challenging” character.

As is known, there are different types of thinking and different forms of thinking depending on how a person thinks: logical, critical, creative, convergent, divergent, verbal, non-verbal, deductive, inductive, analytical, etc. Since critical and creative thinking are among the highest types of thinking, instilling different forms of thinking in students creates conditions for their development. Therefore, each of them is very important in itself and needs to be formed in the student. It should be borne in mind that a person does not use only one type of thinking when thinking. Let us illustrate these considerations presented on the topic of “Solving quadratic equations by the method of factoring”.

The following example is studied together with the students: $(x + 3)(x + 4) = x^2 + 3x + 4x + 3 \cdot 4 = x^2 + (3 + 4)x + 3 \cdot 4 = x^2 + 7x + 12$. This can be written in general as $x^2 + (m + n)x + m \cdot n$. The teacher presents the following information to the students with reference to the studied example and argues it with examples so that the students can assimilate this information: to factor the left side of the equation $x^2 + bx + c = 0$, we need to find two numbers (if such numbers exist) such that their product is equal to c and their sum is equal to b . If b and c are integers, then m and n are integers. In this case, since $x^2 + bx + c = (x + m)(x + n)$, the given equation can be solved by writing it in the form $(x + m)(x + n) = 0$

Example 1. $b > 0, c > 0, x^2 + 6x + 8 = 0, b = 6, c = 8$, since b and c are positive numbers, we need to find two positive numbers such that their product is 8 and their sum is 6. These numbers are 2 and 4. Since $(x + 2)(x + 4) = x^2 + 6x + 8$ is, we write the equation in the form $(x + 2)(x + 4) = 0$ and get $x_1 = -2, x_2 = -4$.

Example 2. $b < 0, c > 0, x^2 - 9x + 18 = 0$, since b is negative and c is positive, we need to find two negative numbers such that the product is 18 and the sum is -9. Since $(x - 3)(x - 6) = x^2 - 9x + 18$, the equation can be written as $(x - 3)(x - 6) = 0$. From here, we get $x_1 = 3, x_2 = 6$.

Example 3. $b > 0, c < 0, x^2 + 5x - 14 = 0$
 $(x - 2)(x + 7) = x^2 + 5x - 14$ and $(x - 2)(x + 7) = 0$ the solution of the equation is $x_1 = 2, x_2 = -7$.

Example 4. $b < 0, c < 0, x^2 - 4x - 21 = 0$
 From the equation $(x - 7)(x + 3) = x^2 - 4x - 21$ and $(x - 7)(x + 3) = 0, x_1 = 7, x_2 = -3$.

In the further course of the lesson, it is recommended to include the following questions, issues, and exercises with the following requirements and content in the tasks aimed at developing the intended skills in students, which are used as a means of organizing whole-class or group work:

☞ Solve quadratic equations by factoring the left side into its components.

☞ The roots of a quadratic equation of the form $(x - m)(x - n) = 0$, with the left side divided into its components, are equal to the numbers m and n . Write the quadratic equations based on the given roots.

☞ Write numbers in place of k such that the roots of the equation are whole numbers (For example: $x^2 + kx + 24 = 0$).

☞ The area of the rectangle is $28 m^2$. What integers can the sides of this rectangle be?

☞ Using the abbreviated multiplication formulas, decompose the left side into its factors and solve the equation (For example: $(x + 3)^2 + (x + 3) - 54 = 0$).

It is recommended that the solution of equations of the form $ax^2 + bx + c = 0$ by the factorization method be investigated first on a field model.

In this process, carried out in the second lesson, the student imagines the multiplication of the trinomial as the lengths of the sides of the rectangle.

Information on the method of factoring equations $ax^2 + bx + c = 0$ is brought to the attention of students in the following content, and examples selected according to a special rule are included to increase the level of awareness and activity of students in the process of mastering: To factor the left side of the equation $ax^2 + bx + c = 0$, it is necessary to find two numbers such that (if any), their product is equal to $a \cdot c$ and their sum is equal to b .

In this case, it can be solved by writing it in the form $ax^2 + bx + c = (ax + m)\left(x + \frac{n}{a}\right) = 0$.

Example 1. Solve the equation $2x^2 + 6x + 4 = 0$.

Let's write it as $2x^2 + 6x + 4 = 2x^2 + mx + nx + 4$. m and n are numbers such that $mn = ac, m + n = b$. In this case $mn = 2 \cdot 4 = 8, m + n = 6$

$2x^2 + mx + nx + 4 = 2x^2 + 2x + 4 = (2x^2 + 2x) + (4x + 4) = 2x(x + 1) + 4(x + 1) = (x + 1)(2x + 4)$;

$(2x + 4)(x + 1) = 0; 2x + 4 = 0, x_1 = -2; x + 1 = 0, x_2 = -1$.

Example 2. Since $4x^2 - 13x + 10 = 0, a = 4, b = -13, c = 10; ac = 4 \cdot 10 = 40, b = -13$ both m and n numbers must be negative. From the pair of negative integers whose product is 40, let's choose the one whose sum is -13. These numbers are -5 and -8.

$4x^2 - 13x + 10 = 4x^2 - 5x - 8x + 10$
 $= x(4x - 5) - 2(4x - 5)$
 $= (4x - 5)(x - 2)$
 $(4x - 5)(x - 2) = 0; 4x - 5 = 0, x_1 = 1,25; x - 2 = 0, x_2 = 2$.

Example 3. In the trinomial $4x^2 - 5x + 4; mn = 16, m + n = -5$; Let's write a list of factors of 16 with negative integers.

As can be seen, there are no integers that satisfy the conditions $mn = 16, m + n = -5$. Therefore, it is impossible to factor this trinomial using integers.

Research. 1) Examine the truth of the following propositions by giving examples. If the proposition is false, change it so that it becomes true.

a) If a and b are natural numbers, the root of the equation $x + a = b$ is a natural number; b) If a and b are integers, the root of the equation $ax = b$ is an integer; c) If a is a non-negative rational number, the root of the equation $x^2 = a$ is a rational number; d) If a is a non-negative real number, the root of the equation $x^2 = a$ is a real number;

2) Is there a real number whose square is equal to -1?

3) a) If $a < 0$, does the equation $x^2 = a$ have a real root? b) Is it possible to solve this problem by expanding the real numbers to a certain set?

4) There is a one-to-one correspondence between the set of real numbers and the points on the number line. What numbers can be associated with the points on the coordinate plane?

The implementation of the research task is summarized by the teacher, and as a result, they have the opportunity to rise to the level of the subject of the information below.

Informative explanation (interpretation) to be addressed to students: After getting acquainted with the

concept of natural numbers, which is considered one of the first concepts of mathematics, we emphasized that the sum and product of any two natural numbers are natural numbers, but their difference may not be a natural number. In other words, if a and b are natural numbers, the equation $a - b = c$ may not have a solution in the set of natural numbers. Therefore, by introducing the concepts of zero and negative integers, the concept of the set of integers was given.

In this set, it is already possible to give the concept of the solution of the equation $x + a = b$ for any a and b integers. However, if a and b are integers and $a \neq 0$, the equation $ax = b$ may not have a solution in the set of integers, that is, for any integers $a \neq 0$, $\frac{b}{a}$ is not always an integer. Therefore, by introducing the concept of a fractional number, the set of integers was expanded to the set of rational numbers. Then it turned out that the equation $x^2 = m$ may not have a root in this set for some positive rational numbers m (for example, the equation $x^2 = 2$ has no root in the set of rational numbers), and therefore, by introducing the concept of irrational numbers, the set of rational numbers was expanded to the set of real numbers. However, this did not completely solve the problem. For example, the existence of a root in the set of real numbers of a quadratic equation $ax^2 + bx + c = 0$ depends on the sign of its discriminant $D = b^2 - 4ac$. It was shown that if $D > 0$, the equation has two different real roots, if $D = 0$, the equation has two equal real roots, and if $D < 0$, the equation has no real roots.

Note that not only some quadratic equations, but also many equations with degree greater than two may not have roots in the set of real numbers. This necessitates the expansion of the set of real numbers. Moreover, this expansion must be such that the operations performed on real numbers are preserved and any equation with degree greater than one in this new set has a root. The simplest of such equations is the equation $x^2 + 1 = 0$ or $x^2 = -1$.

It is clear that this equation has no root in the set of real numbers, because there is no real number whose square is equal to (-1) . Therefore, it is necessary to expand the set of real numbers in such a way that this equation has a root in that set. For this purpose, a new number i is introduced, which is assumed that $x^2 + 1 = 0$ is a root of the equation, that is, $i^2 = -1$. The introduced number i is called the imaginary unit.

One of the important points in teaching the subject is to teach the students the concept of “complex numbers” and operations on them. For this purpose, the teacher tells the students: let's expand the set of real numbers in such a way that all real numbers and the number i are included in this set, and also that the properties of addition and multiplication operations are preserved in this set. For this, if a and b are any real numbers, let's include the “product” of bi and “sum” of $a + bi$ in the new set, and for now, conditionally call the expression $a + bi$ a complex number. 1) First of all, let's assume that the equality for complex numbers $a + bi, c + di$ is true if and only if $a = c, b = d$; 2) The sum of complex numbers $a + bi$ and $c + di$ is called a complex number $(a + c) + (b + d)i$, that is $(a + bi) + (c + di) = (a + c) + (b + d)i$; 3) The product

of complex numbers $a + bi$ and $c + di$ is called a complex number $ac - bd + (ad + bc)i$, that is $(a + bi)(c + di) = ac - bd + (ad + bc)i$

Note that these operations are similar to operations performed on binomials, assuming $i^2 = -1$ in multiplication.

Scientific novelty of the research. 1) The idea that education (which is a system understood as the process, result, and value of sharing human experience) is a superstructure in the system (basis) of socio-economic relations that was formed adequately to the challenges of the industrial revolutions, and 2) the correspondence of the basic organizational form, which is among its components, to the emergent nature of education (superstructure), has been identified as an element of the theory developed by the field of pedagogical science.

Practical significance of the research. Practical educators will be able to achieve greater efficiency (results) by referring to scientific innovation obtained in research in the process of organizing and managing training.

Conclusion. 1) The concept of “modern education” is relative, this concept is determined by its compliance with industrial revolutions, its paradigm of existence can be modeled as “Stages of development of civilization \Leftrightarrow system of social relations \Leftrightarrow sharing of human experience”; 2) The main feature of the training system, which is understood as a way to implement “modern education”, is that it is “learner-centered” and includes a (vectorial) change in the direction of “opportunity-action-new quality”; 3) The component included in the training system as “its main organizational form” is conditioned by the “dialectics of the system-structural approach”.

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